

Industrial Cluster With System Dynamic Approach To Improve Competitiveness: Study On The Micro -And Small-Scale Ethanol Industry In Sukoharjo, Indonesia

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Abstract: MSMEs initiate economic expansion; however, several challenges in the bioethanol sector, such as exorbitant cost, unstable supply of raw materials, outdated technology, and insufficient market access, are faced frequently. While previous studies on MSME competitiveness have primarily applied static models such as Porter's Diamond, these approaches fail to capture the dynamic interactions shaping industrial performance over time. This research works to close this gap by systematically linking Industrial Cluster Theory and SD modelling to measure MSEs' competitiveness in Sukoharjo, Indonesia. With a mixed method, stakeholder interviews were conducted to develop a Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) of major linkages that will provide a basis for quantitative SD simulations dependent on stakeholder input. Results show that the industry's sustainability is governed by cost-effectiveness, security of resources and marketability. The findings highlight the need for structured industrial clustering to address issues such as fragmentation, improved supply chain coordination, and targeted government interventions to support technology adoption, funding, and market expansion. The resulting framework constitutes a dynamic tool for policymakers and industry practitioners to enhance MSE competitiveness and sustainability.

Keywords: industrial clusters; industry competitiveness; micro and small ethanol industries; micro small and medium enterprises (MSMEs); Porter's diamond model; system dynamics (SD)

1. Introduction

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are fundamental to economic development globally, contributing to employment generation and poverty reduction. Enterprises constitute roughly 70% of total employment in developing nations and provide the backbone for sustainable economic growth^{1,2}. Yet, with substantial contributions come enormous challenges, and MSEs still struggle with significant problems, including financial instability, low technology adoption, and limited access to global markets that challenge their long-term competitiveness and growth^{3,4}.

In Indonesia, MSMEs contribute 18.3% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) as of 2022 and employ more than 9.42 million workers in micro and small-scale industries^{5,6}. This reflects the role of these enterprises as a bedrock

of the local economy through encouraging entrepreneurship and improving supply chains and sectoral diversification. One of the prominent sectors in which MSMEs have immense potential is the bioethanol industry, which has been identified as a potential way forward to develop renewable energy and promote sustainable industrialisation⁷. However, the MSMEs contributing to the bioethanol sector are plagued with myriad issues restricting their market competitiveness.

Micro and small-scale ethanol industries still face substantial structural and operational inefficiencies that reduce their competitiveness. Their sustainability is compromised by high production costs, intense competition for raw materials, poor application of advanced technologies (where even the largest companies use outdated production processes), and poor market integration⁸⁻¹⁰. Due to inconsistent production quality,

enterprises face low demand and decreasing profitability. This problem is particularly significant in Sukoharjo, Central Java, Indonesia, where bioethanol production is concentrated. The district is home to some 160 ethanol-producing micro and small Enterprises (MSEs) spread mostly across Mojolaban and Polokarto sub-districts. Although some enterprises have obtained legal permits to produce technical ethanol with a high content of 70%-90% alcohol, most enterprises are still producing 30% alcohol ethanol, which is mainly limited by elements such as production technology, management level, and economic strength. These limitations also lead to higher production costs, unstable product quality, and lower competitive capabilities, which hinder these enterprises' market expansion ^{1,5,6)}.

Fostering cooperation among Indigenous MSEs and optimising resource use and technology have become the dominant strategies for enhancing the competitiveness of the MSEs. For some countries, this has been achieved using Industrial Clustering. The model of Industrial Clusters enables MSEs, through knowledge sharing, supply chain integration, and economies of scale, to improve their productivity and sustainability over the long term ^{1,11)}. This model has also been widely accepted in other areas, such as bioethanol production, where clustering mechanisms have enhanced whole industries' innovative efficiency and competitiveness ⁷⁾. One area where industrial clustering is effective is in the bioethanol sector, but the application is still limited in many developing countries such as Indonesia. The problem of insufficient integration of MSEs into clusters has caused several inefficiencies that have become obstacles to further growth and competitiveness in the markets.

Most existing competitiveness and industrial clustering studies tend to cover large industries or general MSE development. The static models used in these studies, such as Porter's Diamond Model, may be able to identify competitive elements within an industry; however, it does not capture how the components of an industry dynamically interact over time ¹²⁻¹⁴⁾. Micro and small enterprise levels, although there is little research on bioethanol clusters in developing countries. Existing literature has typically explored competitiveness at the macro level, focusing on finalised policy recommendations, providing little grounding on the micro-level mechanisms generating industrial performance ¹⁵⁻¹⁹⁾. This study aims to fill this gap in the literature, providing a more empirically grounded, division of labour perspective on the bioethanol industry at the MSE level. This study makes a novel contribution to the existing body of knowledge by integrating Industrial Cluster Theory and System Dynamics (SD) modelling to examine the competitiveness of micro- and small-scale bioethanol industries. Unlike traditional static models, which provide a snapshot of competitiveness based on fixed parameters,

the SD approach offers an innovative and dynamic framework to assess how various factors, such as production efficiency, raw material availability, market demand, and policy interventions, interact over time to shape industry performance. By pioneering the application of this approach to the ethanol MSE cluster in Sukoharjo, this study provides fresh insights into the systemic challenges these enterprises face and develops a transformative problem-solving model to enhance their competitiveness.

In addition, while previous research has been performed on macro-level policy implications ²⁰⁾ this research is localised, exploring challenges and opportunities from the bioethanol MSE cluster in Sukoharjo. Hence, this research intends to produce actionable implications to understand policies and business manoeuvres more effectively through field data, stakeholder perception, and contextual consideration ^{12,14)}. The results of this study will be highly important to policymakers, industry practitioners as well as MSE operator stakeholders who are interested in strengthening the bioethanol industry through approaches based on clusters and appropriate pooling.

To meet these goals, this study introduces an integrated analytical framework where the principles of industrial clustering and system dynamics modelling principles for assessing and enhancing ethanol MSMEs competitiveness are examined ^{20,21)}. By identifying the key determinants of the success of industrial clusters and putting forth policy recommendations specifically aimed at the micro- and small-scale enterprise level, this research lays the groundwork for improving the bioethanol industry's sustainability in Indonesia and elsewhere.

2. Literatur Review

2.1. Industrial Clusters and Competitiveness

Michael E. Porter's concept of industrial clusters emphasises the geographic concentration of businesses, suppliers, and institutions that enhance productivity and competitiveness. Studies in developed countries highlight that industrial clusters facilitate innovation, strengthen business networks, and improve market penetration ²²⁾. However, in developing countries, implementing cluster models presents challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited financing, and weak policy support ²³⁾.

Empirical studies confirm the advantages of industrial clusters in various industries, including bioethanol production ^{22,24)}. Some studies underscore how bioethanol industrial clusters in developing regions require strong policy support, technological adaptation, and institutional collaboration, as demonstrated in countries like Brazil, Mexico, and Indonesia ^{16,18,25)}. In the case of micro and small enterprises (MSEs) in the bioethanol industry, maintaining strong supplier relationships, adopting

efficient fermentation and separation technologies, and receiving government incentives (e.g., tax subsidies and grants) are key success factors ¹⁶. Brazil's bioethanol industry has also demonstrated how industrial yeast strains can be optimised for large-scale production, highlighting the importance of technological adaptation in industrial clusters ²⁶.

Michael E. Porter highlighted the importance of industrial clusters by describing their geographic concentration, which consists of businesses, suppliers, and institutions, and boosts productivity and competitiveness for the firms. Research conducted in developed areas indicates that industrial clusters promote innovation, reinforce business relationships, and enhance market access ²². However, the application of cluster models in developing nations faces issues like poor infrastructure, insufficient funding, and lack of policy endorsement ²³.

Different studies confirm the presence of industrial clusters in an array of economic activities, one of which is bioethanol production ^{22,24}. Some literature highlights the bioethanol industrial clusters that exist in developing regions, which need aggressive policy intervention, technology modification, and institutional collaboration, as witnessed in Brazil, Mexico, and Indonesia ^{16,18,25}. For MSEs in the bioethanol industry, the ability to maintain strong supplier linkages, efficient fermentation and separation processes, and government support (tax incentives and grants) lead to success ^{16,18,25}. For instance, industrial yeast strains in Brazil's bioethanol industry can be readily produced in bulk, illustrating how industrial clusters adapt technology to meet the needs of different industries ²⁶.

Some studies revealed that the cluster's competitive advantages result from government support, existing incentives, knowledge networks, and supplier integration ¹⁷. Competitiveness in MSE bioethanol clusters is not determined only by cost efficiency but also by the combination of other factors, such as the availability of raw materials, technology, and government intervention ²⁷. These factors will be the foundation of this study's competitiveness.

2.2. The Porter's Diamond Model and Industry Competitiveness

The development of industrial clusters has been examined by the external environment and other governmental actions that affect the cluster's viability over time ²⁸. Porter's Diamond Model identifies competitiveness with four factors: factor conditions, demand conditions, related and supporting industries, and firm strategy and rivalry ²⁷. Regional policy facilitates joint-venture activities of firms, which results in greater industrial competitiveness ²⁹. Similarly, social capital is important for successful regions where trust and open communication enhance collaboration and productivity ³⁰.

Merging the cluster industrial theory and system dynamics with the bioethanol industry offers greater insight into the influence of market, regulation, and technology change on MSE competitiveness ¹⁰. Despite the usefulness of the Diamond Model in competitiveness assessment, its rigidity is in the static features, which is a problem for many industries undergoing fast-moving markets, changing regulations, and volatile technology ¹². This study utilises this approach to address the bioethanol cluster's sustainability issues.

Diamond Porter's model is static, so the research incorporates system dynamics to model causal relations and develop the competitiveness of supply chain systems for long-term competitiveness and policy actions. The research makes the point that the bioethanol sector's competitive advantage cannot be considered only from the perspective of interindustry competition ¹⁴. Consequently, incorporating other analysis models into Porter's is necessary for assessing the competitiveness of bioethanol clusters over time.

2.3. System Dynamics in Industrial Competitiveness

Forrester developed the System Dynamics (SD) approach in 1960 to provide a model for solving problems regarding the intricate relationships within industrial systems. It has also been applied to economics and other fields, such as policy and organisational studies, to understand the relationship between different variables over time ^{11,31}. They are useful in analysing MSEs and high-complexity environments like the bioethanol industry.

A fundamental feature of SD is the so-called stocks and flows concept, which pertains to the mobilisation of inputs and outputs within a sector ²⁰. Also, feedback loops amplify or dampen industrial activity change ³². For MSEs with restricted financial, technological and operations management resources, SD models effectively analyse complex system dynamics within their business context ³³.

Causal Loop Diagrams (CLDs) presented in this study capture the main aspects of competitiveness in the context of MSE bioethanol production by integrating elements such as production costs, availability of raw materials, governmental policies, and market supply. CLDs are more comprehensive than traditional static constructs like Porter's Diamond because they include the interplay between the system's components and changes in the supply chain, the market, and policies ¹⁷.

This research proposes a new analytical framework for bioethanol MSE clusters combining Porter's Diamond with the SD model that can aid policymakers in designing systematic strategies targeting the clusters. The SD model allows for better representation of bioethanol clusters' behaviour to external shocks such as changes in raw material costs or modification of environmental legislation.

3. Methods

3.1. Research Design

This research aims to assess the competitive advantage of micro and small enterprises (MSEs) in the bioethanol industry from a supply chain perspective. The assessment uses Porter's Diamond Model by measuring the industry's competitive position through its key determinants: factor conditions, demand conditions, related and supporting industries, and the firm's strategy, structure, and rivalry. This structure helps determine what resources, market conditions, and industrial relations MSEs can exploit to enhance their competitiveness^{13,34}.

The diamond model has challenges when applied to rapidly changing industries, such as bioethanol^{7,19}. It is a static model and does not contain feedback loops that include external shocks or cyclical market changes that affect industry competition over time. Considering these constraints, the research incorporates system dynamics to model causal relations and develop the competitiveness of supply chain systems for long-term competitiveness and policy actions^{33,35}.

At this analysis stage, the Industrial Cluster Theory is integrated as it explains how the location and relations of firms, suppliers, and institutions affect competitiveness. The presence of industrial clusters allows the sharing of resources, coordination of the supply chain, and dissemination of information, which increases efficiency, innovation, and market access to bioethanol MSEs³⁶.

The study was conducted using a mixed approach, whereby primary data was collected through a systematic questionnaire survey executed on selected industry actors. Participants of the study include representatives of government agencies, members of industry associations, and owners of ethanol MSEs to help provide a thorough view of supply chain competitiveness^{35,37}.

Primary data were collected through in-depth interviews with 30 people, including the leaders and staff at the Sukoharjo Regency Industry and Manpower Office (6 people), leaders and staff at the Trade, Cooperatives and MSMEs Office of Sukoharjo Regency (4 people), ethanol MSE owners in Bekonang Village, Mojolaban (8 people) and the chairman and members of the micro- and Small-Scale Ethanol Industry Association of Mojolaban (12 people).

For collection data, a questionnaire was developed based on Porter's Diamond Model and Industrial Cluster Theory to assess the competitiveness of the micro and small-scale bioethanol industry. The instrument validation process was carried out using a pilot testing method on a small group of ethanol craftsmen to ensure understanding of the questions asked in the survey³⁸. Feedback from this trial was used to refine the instrument before being applied to a wider range of respondents.

The results of surveys will help shape the Causal Loop

Diagram (CLD). A CLD is constructed to show feedback relationships between the most critical factors of an industry^{11,39}, which are needed to develop a dynamic simulation model designed to evaluate the impact of policy and market changes in the bioethanol industry³⁸. Porter's Diamond Model derives the justification for selecting significant parameters inside the bioethanol CLD subsystem. Such a model assists in comprehending competitive advantage by looking at the nexus of several variables determining an industry's productivity. Evidence from surveys and interviews conducted within the bioethanol industry proves these parameters are critical issues^{20,38}.

Subsystem (1) outlines the correlation between efficiency and lowered production costs, generating higher profits for MSEs and enhancing their capacity to invest in new technology and procure better-quality raw materials^{23,36}. This subsystem can become a crucial element for achieving systemic quality enhancement. Subsystem (2) emphasises the existence of adequately sufficient markets. The government can step in and open new demand with appropriate regulations. Therefore, this subsystem is also a key factor that needs attention¹⁴. Subsystem (3) is related to enhancing the quality of the raw materials, which is hoped to yield better quality products and, in the end, increase the profits of MSEs⁴⁰. Subsystem (4) maintains the supply of raw materials and profits from lowered prices of raw materials. The two basic concepts are maintenance and low prices of the raw materials⁴⁰.

In any case, Porter's Diamond Model and empirical evidence corroborate these four parameters' choices as critical issues in the CLD bioethanol subsystem. The interaction of cost efficiency, demand sufficiency, availability of raw materials, and profits demonstrates the complexity of the bioethanol industry in which internal firm activities and external market conditions define competitive advantage^{33,35,41}. The survey and interview evidence indicates a clear need for a comprehensive response to these challenges through strategic policy, supply chain, and market intervention to stabilise the industry and promote growth.

This study was accomplished by integrating Porter's diamond model, industrial cluster theory, and system dynamics to develop a practical analysis to understand the competition among bioethanol MSEs for use by industry and regulatory decision-makers.

3.2. Industrial Clusters Analysis Method

Additionally, by examining bioethanol industry competitiveness, the study highlights the effect of geographic concentration and inter-firm networks on industry performance. The study also probes into the role of government policy, regulatory interventions, and investment incentives toward the sustainability and profitability of bioethanol clusters in the long term.

Considering innovation, investment fraud, and rapid market transformation, collaboration among cluster members is examined to ascertain its influence on new enterprise development⁴²⁻⁴⁴).

The industrial cluster analysis method is especially suitable for this analysis, as it helps determine how the bioethanol industry stands compared to other industries worldwide. Bioethanol concentration focuses on competitive position and the combination of clusters and industries, their value chain, the level of spending on technology, and their productivity rates^{20,35,45}).

The study adopts a combination of System Dynamics and Industrial Cluster Theory to understand the changes in the competitiveness of bioethanol clusters. This interdisciplinary combination enables analysis of the interaction between firms and their environment from a longitudinal perspective. It serves as a basis for evaluating resource allocation, growth of an industry, and competition outcomes as a consequence of policies implemented^{46,47}). The results will create an actionable strategy for policymakers and industry participants that assists and controls the industrial development of the cluster to build a competitive and innovation-oriented bioethanol industry.

3.3. Adapting Porter's Diamond Model to Industrial Clusters

Porter's Diamond Model considers a competitive advantage concerning an industry by breaking down the factor conditions, demand conditions, related and supporting industries, and firm strategy, structure, and rivalry. These components operate within industrial clusters and define their innovation, competition, and long-run growth potential. Governments and global markets also impact cluster competitiveness because they influence the other market and firm behaviour factors¹²).

By illustrating how industrial clusters use these competitive advantages, the model sets a guide for productivity. Local and foreign market conditions dictate the industry's specialisation and the improvements of its products, which in turn determines the demand. Unrelated and supporting industries improve productivity through supplier and knowledge spillovers, and firm strategies and competition foster innovation and competitiveness^{19,36}).

Michael Porter's "Diamond Model" is a strategic tool that can accurately evaluate critical drivers of competitiveness in the bioethanol sector. Porter's strategic model has four components: Factor Conditions, Demand Conditions, Related and Supporting Industries, and Firm Strategy, Structure, and Rivalry. Moreover, industry competitiveness is heavily influenced by two external forces, Government and Chance Events.

The bioethanol industry can be analysed through Porter's model, where Factor Conditions capture the relevant raw materials (sugarcane or molasses), bioethanol infrastructure, and technology. Demand Conditions

capture the policies, regulations, and overall market demand to which bioethanol is subjected. Related and Supporting Industries comprise the suppliers of raw materials, fermentation technology providers, and even the distribution systems that support the bioethanol sector^{33,35}). Lastly, Firm Strategy, Structure, and Rivalry deal with how business units within an industry compete, innovate, and position themselves within the market¹⁴).

To include the diamond model in the system dynamics approach, essential interactions, such as integrating the elements, have to be represented by key variables. The key variables are established through interviews and surveys designed as a causal loop diagram depicting how the variables interrelate. The parameters were the availability and cost of inputs, rate of new technology uses, government support and regulation, pricing and consumption of bioethanol, and rivalry in the industry¹⁴). While simulating industry behaviour over time, decision-makers and business leaders try to predict what the future may look like and what strategies can be employed in light of the myriad of possible outcomes. System Dynamics was useful for modelling these outcomes to understand better the feedback loops, reinforcements that make the problem worse, and what can be done in terms of the policy to improve the competitiveness of the bioethanol industry^{14,35}).

Porter's Diamond Model has weak applicability to MSEs in developing economies because of these regions' structural and institutional constraints. The region's underdeveloped financial systems, poorly integrated supply chains, and weak regulatory frameworks are uncompetitive^{23,48}). The model expects strong institutional backing and the requisite infrastructure, which is absent in emerging economies. A more refined model needs to be employed to fill such gaps, which views industrial clusters as a structural solution to market failures by promoting embeddedness, infrastructure, and finance for MSEs in the cluster.

The effectiveness of strategic interventions in bioethanol industry clusters depends on how well the determinants of the Diamond Model are reinforced. Diamond model factor conditions can be satisfied through workforce training programs and investing in securing raw material supply chains. Demand conditions could be strengthened with government policies such as export incentives and blending mandates, which directly stimulate market growth^{31,35,49}). The cluster can also develop related and supporting industries like logistics, molasses suppliers, and R&D institutions, increasing innovation and efficiency. Moreover, greater competitiveness within the industry is achieved through the availability of an enabling business environment that incorporates collaboration and technological advancement.

Integrating the nuances of developing economies into Porter's Diamond Model ensures that industrial clusters

fully develop their competitiveness. As developed economies face increased market fluctuations, tailor-made policies, infrastructure spending, and sector-specific assistance programmes aid MSEs to withstand market unpredictabilities and promote sustainable development. New bioethanol production industries can adapt to these agglomeration difficulties using this integrated approach and ensure that the primary tenets of the Diamond Model remain pertinent in underdeveloped economies.

3.4. System Dynamics Approach

This research applies System Dynamics (SD) modelling techniques to analyse MSEs' learning gaps and experiences in bioethanol industry clusters. Through these SD models, one can analyse the interrelationship between the industry's sustainability regarding production capacity, market demand, supply chain productivity, and profitability^{50,51}. A production model teaches that production limits, in conjunction with market saturation, MSE pricing structures, and cost structures, can be coordinated in such a manner as to reduce costs and increase profits simultaneously.

In addition, the model captures explicitly some supply chain processes and shows how they can constrain the availability of materials. These fundamental insights assist MSEs to improve their agile and lean operational capabilities²⁰. The market and economic performance analysis are another critical aspect of the model. Analysis of the market and income performance enables the users to plan investment expenditure for income for a particular case scenario, thus assisting in allocation planning. Consequently, MSEs are better poised to manage their core business activities while mitigating associated risks⁴⁹.

The model incorporates exogenous variables such as government intervention and environmental policies, which help the MSEs assess the impacts of policy compliance and determine where policy incentives may be beneficial⁵². Environmental sustainability considerations are also included, corresponding with the international calls for better ecological performance in the bioethanol industry.

Regarding human resource issues, the model considers the changes in the workforce and the organisational learning necessary for accomplishing the operational targets. This feature builds MSEs' internal capacity and contributes to bioethanol industry clusters' sustainability. Therefore, the SD model is a plan design model that allows MSEs in the bioethanol industry to formulate a comprehensive strategy with economic, environmental, social, and operational goals^{48,49,53,54}.

System verification and validation are essential if often overlooked, aspects of model building within System Dynamics. Its importance stems from the necessity that any model intended to represent an actual system must validate the system it wants to convey. This process

includes checking the model's structure and control systems and evaluating if it captures the system's cause-and-effect relationships and dynamic features. Structure verification concerns confirming the model's components, including the framework's processes, relationships, and parameters^{14,55}. On the other hand, validation of behaviour measures whether the model reproduces known outcomes over time^{55,56}.

Verification and validation steps of the model are carried out in the SFD that has already been constructed²¹. Verification is conducted to check whether the appropriate computer program and conceptual literal representation of a real-life model corresponds to the defined model. This process includes checking the model's structure and control systems and evaluating if it captures the system's cause-and-effect relationships and dynamic features. Verification is concerned with confirming the model's components, including processes, relationships, and parameters that constitute the framework. Verification techniques like those offered by authorities and stakeholders during the survey and the development of CLD are also needed²⁸.

The next phase after verification is model validation. Validating the model means checking if its simulated behaviour agrees with its corresponding real-life system behaviour. Verification is done on the formulation (equation) and units of model variables. Verifying units and equations of the model with Powersim software is performed because this software only allows the execution of models with unit consistency and equation formulation. The model validation uses a quantitative validation approach, the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE)⁵⁶. MAPE estimates the accuracy of a forecasting technique by averaging the absolute percentage error of the model's predictive value compared to the set observed value using the formula:

$$\text{MAPE} = 1/n \sum_{t=1}^n \left(\frac{\text{abs}(X_m - X_d)}{X_d} \right) \times 100 \%$$

X_m = Simulation Results, and X_d = Data

The criteria are:

- $\text{MAPE} < 5 \%$: very appropriate
- $5\% < \text{MAPE} < 10 \%$: Appropriate
- $\text{MAPE} > 10 \%$: Inappropriate

The SD model can uniquely capture an ever-changing industry's complex market feedback systems. In contrast, Porter's Diamond Model and cluster theory focus on the company's competitive advantage and use static models that fail to incorporate outside market shocks or changes over time¹²⁻¹⁴. While relying on the supply chain's causal mapping systems, an SD model offers a framework that provides context for policymaking and competition strategy.

In addition, this study collects primary data through surveys and interviews with industry stakeholders,

including government officials, industry representative bodies, and owners of bioethanol MSEs, to create a Causal Loop Diagram (CLD). The CLD determines critical industry components, captures their interrelationships, and translates them into a dynamic simulation model that estimates the effects of policy and market dynamics on the competitiveness of bioethanol MSEs³⁸).

Conventional models fall short in dealing with uncertainty, but integrating various approaches makes an SD model more adaptable and flexible. This model also provides a useful reference for governmental authorities and industry practitioners and aims to formulate competitive and sustainable business interventions in the bioethanol industry.

4. Result

The primary data were used to define the important variables in the ethanol MSE cluster in Sukoharjo as illustrated in Figure 1. The CLD for the competitiveness of MSE clusters reveals five interrelated important variables (parameters), namely, ethanol production, ethanol demand, molasses availability, profit level and number of ethanol MSEs. These five parameters can be viewed as subsystems that interact with one another to improve the competitiveness of ethanol MSE clusters in Sukoharjo. Specifically, a change in one parameter will affect the other parameters.

4.1. Conceptualisation of The System Through CLD

The causal loop diagram (CLD) illustrates the dynamic interconnections and feedback loops influencing the competitiveness of micro and small ethanol industry clusters⁵⁷). Such CLD helps identify and analyse the interplay among key variables like profit-making ability, production, consumption, resource availability & clustering behaviour. This Feedback Loop diagram shows a mix of (R) and (B) loops that determine ethanol industry behaviour. Reinforcing loops produces growth while balancing loops limit/ equilibrium forces. Looking up at the systemic level, it clearly shows the importance of (favourable) regulatory and financial conditions that external factors, such as investment policy, banking services support policy and laws that will promote prohibition, such as cannabis for profit, prominently dominate the system. Nevertheless, if the product, in this case, is molasses (or in some cases ethanol), sound resource management is key to ensure that production and demand regarding molasses are balanced with minimum shocks to the system. However, effective resource management, especially in molasses and ethanol storage (product), is essential to balance production and demand while reducing shocks to the system.

The following CLD illustrates the rich interplay of factors

as they manifest in the cluster system within a single mode of ethanol. As the global system of ethanol cluster is seen from the whole, it is possible to draw up an entity representation from the system dynamics model, for example, the Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) by being developing in the form of stakeholder engagement (interview) that emphasise the cycle which relates each other that cover multiple influences that affect the competitiveness and sustainability of the industry³⁸). As such, CLD can help inform policymakers, investors, and stakeholders with this knowledge to identify leverage points by increasing economies of scale, availability of resources, and demand via policy incentives. They have improved competitiveness and sustainability for ethanol industry clusters by focusing on these key areas. Figure 1 shows the relationship amongst these variables and their feedback structures.

Fig. 1: Main Causal Loop Diagram

4.2. Simulation Models

This study modelled four subsystems that affect cluster development to improve the competitiveness of ethanol MSEs in Sukoharjo, namely, (1) increasing production cost efficiency, (2) promoting the effect of demand adequacy, (3) optimising the system through the availability of molasses raw materials and (4) optimising the system through increasing profits and availability of molasses raw materials as shown in Figure 2 to Figure 5.

Fig. 2: Subsystem 1. Increasing production cost efficiency

Fig. 3: Subsystem 2. The effect of demand adequacy

Fig. 4: Subsystem 3. Optimising the system through the availability of molasses raw materials

Fig. 5: Subsystem 4. Optimising the system through increasing profits and availability of molasses raw materials

4.3. Model Validation

A conceptual model needs to be validated to confirm its trustworthiness and ability to accurately describe real-world situations. Model dynamics built through the preparation of stock-and-flow diagrams were used to simulate models that can explain the behaviour of variables. Model validation was then performed by comparing the values of the key variables with real conditions⁵⁸⁾ using the MAPE technique. These key variables include the number of cluster members, ethanol production, ethanol production value, molasses usage, production cost, and profit of MSE^{14,21,28,37).}

Table 1: Average Cluster Size Over a Year

Year	Data	Simulation	Result (%)	Description
2018	20,50	20,21	1,40	Total : 8,92 MAPE : 1,49 (Very Appropriate)
2019	21,81	22,63	3,77	
2020	22,88	22,25	2,75	
2021	23,75	23,70	0,23	
2022	24,42	24,49	0,27	
2023	20,20	20,30	0,50	

Source: Survey of MSEs experiences in Sukoharjo, Indonesia

Table 2: Average of Production Ethanol 70% a year

Year	Data	Simulation	Result (%)	Description
2018	59.180,20	58.332,35	1,43	Total : 15,31 MAPE : 2,55 (Very Appropriate)
2019	62.765,41	65.160,28	3,82	
2020	71.214,73	70.286,97	1,30	
2021	76.028,38	73.598,40	3,20	
2022	63.086,79	64.893,36	2,86	
2023	54.662,36	53.188,15	2,70	

Source: Survey of MSEs experiences in Sukoharjo, Indonesia

Table 3: Average of Production Value Ethanol 70% a year

Year	Data	Simulation	Result (%)	Description
2018	1.888.048.297	1.793.274.090	5,02	Total : 33,88 MAPE : 5,65 (Appropriate)
2019	2.118.729.502	2.143.969.285	1,19	
2020	2.334.170.063	2.624.584.273	12,44	
2021	2.535.189.917	2.441.570.875	3,69	
2022	2.201.798.727	2.018.071.868	8,34	
2023	1.849.189.418	1.790.086.792	3,20	

Source: Survey of MSEs experiences in Sukoharjo, Indonesia

Table 4: The Average Profit per Month Over a year

Year	Data	Simulation	Result (%)	Description
2018	22.730.945	23.501.910	3,39	Total : 18,93 MAPE : 3,16 (Very Appropriate)
2019	29.216.827	28.306.500	3,12	
2020	34.754.585	35.796.521	3,00	
2021	36.848.770	35.737.341	3,02	
2022	34.311.477	32.211.133	6,12	
2023	19.551.333	19.497.175	0,28	

Source: Survey of MSEs experiences in Sukoharjo, Indonesia

Table 5: Average of Molasses Usage a year

Year	Data	Simulation	Result (%)	Description
2018	274.901	275.620	0,26	Total : 21,91 MAPE : 3,65 (Very Appropriate)
2019	301.291	327.882	8,83	
2020	331.764	332.105	0,10	
2021	359.234	327.752	8,76	
2022	302.810	306.621	1,26	
2023	258.279	251.314	2,70	

Source: Survey of MSEs experiences in Sukoharjo, Indonesia

Table 6: Average Production Cost per Liter Over a Year

Year	Data	Simulation	Result (%)	Description
2018	20.941,12	21.306,56	1,75	Total : 21,04 MAPE : 3,51 (Very Appropriate)
2019	22.041,11	22.518,78	2,17	
2020	23.155,26	24.628,65	6,36	
2021	22.502,41	23.877,21	6,11	
2022	22.673,16	23.060,73	1,71	
2023	21.068,44	20.448,97	2,94	

Source: Survey of MSEs experiences in Sukoharjo, Indonesia

These MAPE results justify the model's accuracy in depicting the competitive structure of ethanol MSE clusters in Sukoharjo. Hence, this model can analyse the system's movement within set limits. This model can also be applied to analyse the movements in the values of the variables within the defined scenario. The simulation results can show any intervention's effects on particular system variables.

The scenario implemented in this study was to enhance the competitiveness of the ethanol industry cluster by designing a scenario that intervenes in the production econometric model using exogenous variables such as government policy, regulations, incentives, and other supportive actions targeting ethanol-producing MSEs. The scenario measures the status quo (Business as Usual/BAU)

and the resultant impacts following the intervention.

4.4. Sensitivity Analysis

Understanding how changes to exogenous variables (parameters) affect the key variables is one of the requirements in simulation models. In this case, several cases are given to simulate changes to make the right decision^{28,59}). In this study, the following cases were considered in the sensitivity analysis:

4.4.1. 20% production cost efficiency for improving production capacity

Fig. 6: Sensitivity analysis of 20% production cost efficiency

Figure 6 shows that production efficiency is one of the

variables that affect the increase in production capacity and the benefits ⁶⁰⁾ and cluster size. A 20% production cost efficiency increases the profits obtained by ethanol MSEs ⁶¹⁾. The increase in ethanol production drives such increase due to improved production cost efficiency, thus enabling ethanol MSEs to maintain and improve their production capacity in the long term. However, in the long run, the production cost efficiency starts to affect the availability of raw materials for molasses, as reflected in the sharp increases in the number of ethanol craftsmen and molasses consumption.

4.4.2. 10% increase in raw material availability

According to Porter’s diamond model, one of the factor conditions that support the competitiveness of the ethanol industry is the availability of raw materials ⁶²⁾. Ethanol MSEs in Bekonang are challenged by the limited availability of molasses as a raw material and their lack of production process technologies ⁶³⁾. A sensitivity analysis of a 10% increase in raw material availability was carried out to see its effect on the competitiveness of industrial clusters ^{62,63)}.

Fig. 7: Sensitivity analysis of a 10% increase in raw material availability

Results show that such an increase does not affect ethanol production, company profits, the number of artisans or consumption of molasses. The absence of any changes in these trends indicates that the availability of molasses as a raw material will not affect the other variables and will not be affected by the changes in these variables.

4.4.3. Market potential/demand

The production process is highly dependent on the level of demand. Similarly, the growth of the bioethanol market in Bekonang is significantly influenced by potential demand for bioethanol products ⁶⁴⁾. Increasing the market potential by 20% ⁶⁵⁾ changes the amount of ethanol production but does not alter the current growth trend. Similarly, increasing the market potential affects the increase in the number of producers and profits obtained but does not affect the corresponding trends.

Fig. 8: Sensitivity analysis of increasing the market potential by 20%

4.5. Designing policy scenarios for improvement

4.5.1. Scenario 1

Scenarios were created for several variables that are suspected as driving factors in subsystem 1. These scenarios include reducing the production cost by 20%, reducing ethanol prices by 10% and estimating a 30% growth in ethanol market potential.

The simulation results show a relatively stable system with marked profit gains that are relatively sloping (stable) in the range of 15% better than the existing conditions. Likewise, the increase in the number of MSEs producing ethanol at 70% and the ethanol production at the cluster level sharply increased by 100% until the end of the simulation (five years). Increasing ethanol production reached the estimated demand limit of the potential market which when measured by the formulation of demand coverage (production/demand) still shows a Figure 9 which means the market has begun to saturate.

Fig. 9: Simulation results of scenario 1

To measure the stability of the system that was formed based on scenario 1, an intervention was carried out on market potential/demand. If replacing the forecasted 30% growth in demand by a 10% growth does not change the intervention of the other variables, then the behaviour of these variables is changed.

Fig. 10: Simulation results of scenario 1 with potential market intervention

As shown in Figure 10, profit shows a downward trend from the second year to the end of the simulation, during which the trends for the two scenarios become similar. Therefore, market limitations reduced the earnings of MSEs as the market absorption decreased. For MSE's growth in ethanol production, 70% decreased growth by 20% from scenario 1. The doubts of MSE owners regarding the market conditions can be clearly observed at the beginning of the simulation year when the number of cluster members decreased. During this period, ethanol production decreased by around 21%, which was consistent with the results from scenario 1 where the interest of MSEs in producing ethanol decreased by 70% due to market limitations. The demand coverage at the end of the simulation was the same as that in scenario 1, thereby indicating that market absorption decreases in response to market limitations. The market is relatively saturated, thus reducing its absorption.

4.5.2. Scenario 2

In scenario 2, the market was expanded by 15% without conditioning the production capacity capabilities of MSEs, and all other variables were allowed to move as is without any specific intervention.

Fig. 11: Simulation results of scenario 2

Figure 11 shows a smaller growth in the number of cluster members in scenario 2 than in scenario 1. In this case, increasing the number of MSEs producing ethanol at 70% is not optimal because environmental conditions, including production costs, availability of raw materials and other input factors, do not support such target. Likewise, the ethanol selling price did not increase despite the increasing demand. Under these conditions, the 17% increase in

profits is most likely due to an increase in sales volume. As a result, the growth of MSEs decreases in year 4 even though demand coverage has not yet reached a saturation point.

The decrease in the number of MSEs in year 4 also reduced the ethanol production volume. Therefore, increasing the market demand for producing ethanol at 70% does not optimise cluster system capacity. The continuity of meeting the needs of the market cannot be maintained properly, thus resulting in a negative market reaction and affecting the level of acceptance of ethanol products from MSEs.

4.5.3. Scenario 3

In scenario 3, access to molasses as feedstock was improved by 10% to understand the effects of providing molasses as a raw material. Such access affects affordability, that is, every 10% increase in access is always followed by a 2% decrease in molasses prices (increasing affordability at the price level due to increased supply/availability of molasses).

Figure 12 shows no significant differences between the existing conditions and intervention results in terms of cluster size, ethanol production and profit.

Fig. 12: Simulation results of scenario 3

In sum, interventions on molasses availability do not exert a significant impact if done partially (i.e. not followed by other interventions). When viewed from the simulation results for demand coverage, the market is not too saturated because DC is only worth 0.95. Thus, policies that only focus on facilitating the provision of molasses do not effectively promote the optimality of the system as a whole. When implementing such policies, interventions should be applied for other variables, such as offering subsidies for molasses price and increasing the production efficiency of MSEs by improving their equipment and technical ability to produce 70% ethanol.

4.5.4. Scenario 4

In scenario 4, the supply chain was cut to reduce production costs and improve the quality of ethanol products. This scenario aimed to understand the impact of increasing profits due to policies for increasing the ability of MSEs to supply molasses by 10% and reducing molasses prices by 10%. This scenario also considered improvements in the quality of products and the resulting increase in market penetration.

Fig. 13: Simulation results of scenario 4

Figure 13 shows that cutting the supply chain and increasing the ability of MSEs to supply molasses by 10% lead to a 10% decrease in molasses prices and a 16% increase in profits. However, in real scenarios, this intervention would only increase the number of MSE by 30%.

The increase in the number of MSEs is inversely juxtaposed with increase in profits due to limited market absorption (as seen in the comparison between production and demand). The market share is still enjoyed by incumbents, and the market has not grown along with the improved ability of MSEs to produce 70% ethanol.

If the market can respond to the improvement in quality and continuity of 70% ethanol supply, then the increase in market absorption following the production capability of MSEs can be simulated as follows:

Fig. 14: Simulation results of Scenario 4 with increased market ability to absorb 70% ethanol production by MSEs

The above simulation results show that if the market is open due to increasing ethanol production quantity and quality (according to market demand), then the increase in profits will be followed by a 100% increase in the number of MSEs producing 70% ethanol.

The additional interventions carried out in scenario 4 are estimated to have a significant impact on opening new markets for ethanol products. Balancing product quality and quantity with market absorption can maintain the competitiveness of these products and improve cluster optimality.

5. Discussion

The above scenarios highlight production cost efficiency as the most influential factor in improving the

competitiveness of ethanol MSEs in Sukoharjo. Increasing production cost efficiency will reduce the total costs incurred by these MSEs, and such decrease in total cost will increase the ability of these MSEs to lower their selling prices and consequently enhance the competitiveness of their products in the market. Despite reducing their selling price by 10%, the profits of ethanol MSEs continue to increase due to their 20% production cost efficiency. Such increase in profits in turn enhances their investment ability and the capability and capacity of their human resources and production process technologies to meet the market demand.

Elida et al. (2023) identified factor conditions, demand conditions, related and supporting industries, firm structure, strategy and rivalry, government involvement and chance as determining factors in increasing the competitiveness of agro-industrial sago products. Amongst these factors, factor conditions (i.e. physical/natural resources, infrastructure resources, human resources, capital resources and scientific resources) emerged as the most decisive ⁶⁶.

Increasing the capability and capacity of human resources in producing and marketing products will improve the ability of MSEs to meet the market demand. Similarly, increasing the usage of higher-technology production machines will increase the capability and capacity of MSEs to produce quality products at lower prices, thus increasing their competitiveness. Increasing production capability and capacity accompanied by increased market demand and access to raw materials will also affect the survival of these MSEs.

A study of MSEs in China revealed that technology capabilities and organisational size positively affect SME performance and that technology capabilities are related to the performance of companies in the manufacturing industry ⁶⁷. Technology development also plays an important role in enhancing the competitiveness of MSEs and driving their sustainable growth ⁶⁸. Strengthening human resource capacity, accompanied by the use of technology and business diversification, positively contributes to increasing the productivity of SMEs; strengthening human resource capacity, productivity, technology utilisation and business diversification simultaneously is also positively and significantly correlated with the sustainability of these enterprises ⁶⁹. Entrepreneurial skills and e-commerce adoption positively affect the performance of SMEs ⁷⁰. Government support positively affects business survival through marketing and process innovation, and marketing innovation, process innovation and entrepreneurial self-efficacy affect the viability of SMEs, with entrepreneurial self-efficacy exerting the greatest impact on SME survival ⁷¹.

The results for scenarios 2 and 3 show that although market demand and raw material availability are important factors, if the interventions on these two factors are carried out

partially, then they will not produce any significant effect. Increasing market access without an accompanying increase in production capabilities and capacity and availability of raw materials will also have no significant effect on increasing market demand. Similarly, increasing the access to raw materials without an accompanying increase in production capability and capacity will not have any significant effect on production cost efficiency. Therefore, to improve the competitiveness of ethanol MSEs, scenarios 1, 2 and 3 must be implemented simultaneously.

Results for scenario 4 show that increasing the potential benefits, increasing the demand for 70%–90% technical ethanol production and improving access to quality raw materials will encourage MSEs to produce 70%–90% technical ethanol instead of 30%. Doing so will also increase the number of ethanol MSEs included in the cluster.

6. Conclusion

The study uses Industrial Cluster Theory and System Dynamics to analyse the competitiveness of micro and small-scale ethanol enterprises in Sukoharjo, Indonesia. It provides an interactive framework considering factors like production, policy, raw material availability, and market demand. The results show cost-efficient production significantly impacts profit margins and value reinvestment in technological innovation. However, these enterprises face constraints like inadequate market access and inefficient supply chain systems.

The research highlights the potential of industrial clustering to enhance MSEs' resilience through resource sharing, knowledge exchange, and supply chain integration. However, the Sukoharjo ethanol industry faces issues due to excessive fragmentation and self-sufficiency. To address these, coordinated cluster development initiatives, supported by government grants, can improve joint bargaining power, production efficiency, market penetration, operational costs, and product quality.

Ethanol MSEs need a stable supply of raw materials to improve their competitiveness. Contracts between ethanol producers and sugar mills can ensure a steady supply of molasses, mitigating katzenjammer prices and allowing for better long-term planning. Implementing price stabilisation policies and expanding cooperative networks can also mitigate risks associated with volatile input costs. These interventions should be combined with market expansion policies and partnerships with large-scale industries to create sustained demand for home-grown bioethanol. A comprehensive policy envelope combining cost reduction opportunities, supply chain optimisation, and market interventions is essential for long-term industry sustainability.

This research uses System Dynamics modelling to assess

the competitiveness of ethanol MSMEs in a developing economy. It provides insights into factors affecting MSME sustainability and suggests further research to scale up to other regions, especially in countries with bioethanol production. The study aims to improve ethanol MSEs' competitiveness, sustainability, and market share in Indonesia by implementing a systematic cluster-based approach, improving cost efficiency and long-term industrial economic performance. This research could also evaluate the long-term effects of industrial clustering policies on MSME performance.

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Appendix

Survey for Bioethanol Industrial Cluster Development (Factors that Influence Behaviour of Industrial Cluster to Improve Competitiveness). Using Linkert 5 Level.

Questionnaire For Bioethanol Industrial Cluster Development

Number of Interviewers :

Location of Interview :

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Personal Information

Name (Optional) :

Name of Firm :

Gender : Man / Woman Age :

Status : Owner/ Manager / Senior Employee

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Questionnaire for Producers > 70%

No Question

1 How much ethanol is produced and noted by artisans per period (daily, weekly, monthly)? Volume:

4 Ethanol production data is neatly recorded

- 3 Monthly average ethanol production data
- 2 Ethanol production data on a weekly average
- 1 Average daily ethanol production data
- 0 Artisans have no ethanol production data
- 2 What is the production ability and capacity of the craftsman per unit of time?

Production:

Capacity:

- 4 The amount of production above its capacity
- 3 The amount of production according to its capacity
- 2 The amount of production under its capacity
- 1 The amount of production is far below its capacity
- 0 Craftsmen do not know their production capacity
- 3 Is the amount of ethanol production carried out on a fixed basis, according to previous trends, or on an order-based basis?
- 4 Fixed amount of ethanol production per time period

- 3 The amount of ethanol production is adjusted to the order
- 2 The amount of ethanol production is adjusted to the season of high and low demand
- 1 The amount of ethanol production is erratic, adjusted to the available raw materials
- 0 Artisans do not have ethanol production data
- 4 Can the production capacity/capacity be increased?
 - 4 Production capacity/capacity is very likely to be increased because all facilities and infrastructure are already available
 - 3 Production capacity/capacity can be increased
 - 2 Production capacity can be difficult to increase because there are several obstacles
 - 1 Production capacity/capacity is very difficult to increase because the constraints are very large
 - 0 Craftmen do not know whether their abilities/capacities can be increased or not
- 5 Is it necessary to increase the expertise/skills of craftsmen to increase production capacity?
 - 4 Must be improved
 - 3 Improvement of expertise/skills is urgently needed
 - 2 Skill improvement is needed
 - 1 No skill enhancement required
 - 0 Do not know
- 6 To increase production capacity, is it necessary to improve the production process's techniques/technology (machines)?
 - 4 Must be improved
 - 3 Improvement of production techniques/technology is urgently needed
 - 2 Improvement of production techniques/technology is needed
 - 1 No improvement in production techniques/technology is required
 - 0 Do not know
- 7 Is it necessary to increase business capital to increase production capacity?
 - 4 Must be improved
 - 3 It is very necessary to increase business capital
 - 2 An increase in business capital is needed
 - 1 No increase in business capital is required
 - 0 Do not know
- 8 To increase production capacity, is the help of other parties needed (universities, local governments, MSME offices, other institutions)?
 - 4 The help of other parties is urgently needed
 - 3 Need help from other parties
 - 2 Little help is needed from other parties
 - 1 No help is required
 - 0 Do not know
- 9 How is molasses available on the market?
 - 4 Highly guaranteed availability
 - 3 Guaranteed availability
 - 2 Quite guaranteed availability
 - 1 Availability is not guaranteed
 - 0 Do not know
- 10 Is there any price movement of molasses in the market?
 - 4 The price of molasses in the market is very stable
 - 3 The price of molasses in the market is stable
 - 2 The price of molasses in the market is quite stable
 - 1 The price of molasses in the market changes frequently
 - 0 The price of molasses on the market changes very often
- 11 Is the help of other parties needed to ensure the stability of molasse prices?
 - 4 Assistance from other parties is needed to ensure the stability of molasses prices
 - 3 Assistance from other parties is needed to ensure the stability of molasses prices
 - 2 Some assistance from other parties is needed to ensure the stability of molasses prices
 - 1 No assistance from other parties is needed to ensure the stability of molasses prices
 - 0 Do not know
- 12 Are there programs from related parties to maintain the stability of molasses prices in the market?
 - 4 There are many programs to maintain price stability
 - 3 There is a program to maintain the stability of molasses prices from 1 related party
 - 2 There are program initiations to maintain price stability, but it has not been realised
 - 1 There is no program to maintain price stability, but it has not been realised
 - 0 Do not know
- 13 How is molasses storage done?
 - 4 The remaining molasses are stored in the house, placed in a special space provided
 - 3 The remaining molasses is stored in the house, placed in the available free space
 - 2 The remaining molasses is stored in the house, but it can be placed anywhere
 - 1 No special treatment for storage of remaining molasses
 - 0 No molasses left to store
- 14 How is ethanol storage done?
 - 4 The remaining ethanol is stored in the house, placed in a special space provided

- 3 The remaining ethanol is stored in the house, placed in the available empty space
- 2 The remaining ethanol is stored in the house but can be placed anywhere
- 1 No special treatment for residual ethanol storage
- 0 No ethanol left to store
- 15 From the profits or profits obtained, is there anything allocated as additional capital to increase the next production capacity?
- 4 The profits allocated for additional business capital are very large
- 3 Profits allocated for additional large business capital
- 2 The profits allocated for additional business capital are quite large
- 1 A small portion of the profits is allocated for additional business capital
- 0 No profits allocated for additional business capital
- 16 What percentage of profit/profit is allocated as additional capital to increase the next production capacity?
- 4 > 50%
- 3 30% - 50%
- 2 10% - 20%
- 1 0% - 10%
- 0 0%
- 17 What is the quality of ethanol produced by artisans? (very good, good, moderately good/average, not good)
- 4 The quality is excellent
- 3 Good quality
- 2 The quality is quite good
- 1 The quality is not good
- 0 Do not know
- 18 What are the opportunities for artisans to meet market demand?
- 4 The opportunities are huge
- 3 The opportunity is great
- 2 The chances are quite large
- 1 The chances are not great
- 0 Do not know
- Questionnaire for *ciu* producers (30% - 40%)
- No Questions
- 1 How is the availability of molasses on the market?
- 4 Very certain availability
- 3 Certain availability
- 2 Quite certain availability
- 1 Not certain availability
- 0 Do not know
- 2 Is there any movement in the price of molasses on the market?
- 4 The price of molasses on the market is very stable
- 3 The price of molasses on the market is stable
- 2 The price of molasses on the market is relatively stable
- 1 The price of molasses on the market often changes
- 0 The price of molasses on the market changes very often
- 3 Is assistance from other parties needed to ensure the stability of the price of molasses?
- 4 The assistance of other parties is very necessary to ensure the stability of molasses prices
- 3 The assistance of other parties is necessary to ensure the stability of molasses prices
- 2 The assistance of other parties is somewhat necessary to ensure the stability of molasses prices
- 1 The assistance of other parties is not necessary to ensure the stability of molasses prices
- 0 Do not know
- 4 Are there any programs from related parties to maintain the stability of molasses prices in the market?
- 4 There are many programs to maintain price stability
- 3 There is a program to maintain the stability of molasses prices from 1 related party
- 2 There is an initiation of a program to maintain price stability, but it has not been realised
- 1 There is no program to maintain price stability, but it has not been realised
- 0 Do not know
- 5 How is molasses stored?
- 4 The remaining molasses is stored in the house, placed in a special room provided
- 3 The remaining molasses is stored in the house, placed in an available empty room
- 2 The remaining molasses is stored in the house but can be placed anywhere
- 1 There is no special treatment for storing the remaining molasses
- 0 There is no molasses left to be stored
- 6 Is any of the profits obtained allocated as additional capital to increase production capacity further?
- 4 The profit allocated for additional business capital is very large
- 3 The profit allocated for additional business capital is large
- 2 The profit allocated for additional business capital is quite large
- 1 A small portion of the profit is allocated for additional business capital
- 0 There is no profit allocated for additional business capital

- 7 What percentage of profit is allocated as additional capital to increase production capacity?
- 4 > 50%
 - 3 30% - 50%
 - 2 10% - 20%
 - 1 0% - 10%
 - 0 0%
- 8 Are craftsmen interested in producing ethanol with a content of > 70%?
- 4 Very interested
 - 3 Interested
 - 2 Quite interested
 - 1 Not interested
 - 0 Very uninterested
- 9 Are there any obstacles to increasing production capacity from ciu (30% - 40%) production to ethanol production with a content of > 70%?
- 4 No obstacles
 - 3 There are a few obstacles
 - 2 There are quite a lot of obstacles
 - 1 There are many obstacles
 - 0 There are very many obstacles
- 10 Is assistance from other parties (universities, local governments, SMEs offices, and other institutions) needed to increase production capacity?
- 4 Help from other parties is really needed
 - 3 Requires assistance from other parties
 - 2 Little assistance is needed from other parties
 - 1 No assistance from other parties is required
 - 0 Do not know
- 11 Is there a profit opportunity if production is increased to ethanol production > 70%?
- 4 The profit opportunities are very large
 - 3 The profit opportunities are quite large
 - 2 There is little opportunity for profit
 - 1 No profit opportunities
 - 0 Do not know